

AS PART OF THE CLEARING HOUSE
PROJECT.....

CLEARINGHOUSE
中欧城市森林应对方案

CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP

SEPTEMBER 8 | 9H AUDITORIUM X

FOR MORE INFORMATION...